

BRAIN TO BRAIN COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

BRAIN TO BRAIN COMMUNICATION

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Keywords: Brain to brain communication, Motor imagery, BCI, Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation

In this study we explore the idea of direct brain to brain communication using what is known as Brain to Brain Interface. Brain to Brain Interface is an integration between a Brain to Computer Interface and a Computer to Brain Interface. For the Brain to Computer interface, we have used Motor Imagery signals extracted via EEG. Computer to Brain Interface is achieved by Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation. Therefore a Transcranial Magnetic Device is developed as part of the project.

Motor Imagery based Brain to Computer Interface is intended to classify between two motor imagery tasks. That is the closing of left vs. right fist. Real time EEG is acquired from the subject who is performing the motor imagery task and pre-processed. Different classifiers which use different features are being tested to decide on the best classifier. A wavelet based Neural Network has shown to classify considerably well compared to the other classifiers tested. Input to this classifier is feature vector composed of different measures calculated using wavelet transformed signal. A maximum classification accuracy of 71% was recorded with Coiflet wavelets for a network with 20 neurons in the hidden layer.

Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation Device is intended to cause a muscle twitch in a second subject. The device creates a strong localized magnetic field over the motor cortex of the subject. The Figure 8 coil that would create intended magnetic field with maximum intensities and focality was designed. The intended high current pulse is obtained by discharging a capacitor bank. A silicon controlled rectifier is used for switching of pulse generator circuit. By discharging the capacitor bank with capacitance of 1800 μ F charged to 610V a monophasic current pulse with peak current of 7kA can be obtained.

To our supervisor
Dr. Anjula De Silva
And
To our parents.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BCI-Brain to Computer Interface

CBI- Computer to Brain Interface

BBI- Brain to Brain interface

TMS- Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation

SCR- Silicon Controlled Rectifier

ERD- Event Related Desynchronization

ERS- Event Related Synchronization

USB- Universal Serial Bus

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter explains the orientation to the research process by highlighting the purpose and importance of the study, the objectives and the scope of the research. It contextualizes the background to the study by including all the terms and definitions related to Brain to Brain Communication and the technologies that being used for the study. The safety issues, risks and side effects of using Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation for Computer to Brain Interface are discussed in the next section. Finally, it specifies the end solution and the potential customers of brain to brain communication system.

1.1 Motivation

The topic of Advance human communication has been receiving close review for many years. This field of research undergoes intense study to increase the range of audiences that one can reach. As a result, we can see a considerable improvement in the available technologies for human to human communication, and also it has helped broadening the audiences that one can reach.

However, the majority of the existing technologies are constrained by the linguistic ability of an individual, the ability to use and understand the language. Most of the information processed in our brain is not introspectively available to our consciousness. Therefore it is not possible for us to convert them in to linguistic form. For instance, knowledge about our fine motor movements/control is not available to our consciousness. Hence it is not possible for us to express them in any linguistic form. If this was not the case, a trained surgeon could easily ‘tell’ a novice how exactly he/she should position and move his/her fingers during the execution of a critical surgery. Also a skilled violinist could easily ‘tell’ the precise finger motor movements to his/her students.

At times, even the information/knowledge which is introspectively available to our consciousness can also be difficult to express in words. Professors with brilliant minds may still struggle to convert complex scientific ideas into linguistic form, even

though they fully understand the concepts. We all are familiar with how difficult it is to express some feelings/emotions in words. This is a fine example of how linguistic ability limits communication.

1.2 Objectives and Scope

Is it possible for this information available to one's brain to be directly transferred into another's brain, without any form of linguistic assistance? Primary objective of this study is to explore this concept.

This objective could possibly be realized by coupling a Brain to Computer Interface with a Computer to Brain Interface. The coupled system is referred to as a Brain to Brain Interface. The following are the objectives realized under the project.

- Design, simulate and implement motor imagery based Brain to Computer Interface (BCI)
- Design, simulate and implement single pulse transcranial magnetic stimulation device as Computer to Brain Interface (CBI)
- Integrate both BCI and CBI together and implement brain to brain communication systems
- Design and implement enclosures for the system

1.3 Brain to Computer Interface (BCI)

Brain computer interface is a communication system that reads brain signals and converts them into control and communication signals. Brain signal acquisition system and the Algorithm that translates the brain signals to meaningful commands are the two major components of a BCI system. There are many ways to categorize Brain to Computer Interfaces. One way is to categorize depending on the type of brain signal the system is interested in. Three most commonly used signals are Steady State Visually Evoked Potentials, P300 and Motor Imagery Signals. The former two signals are evoked as a response to an external stimulus whereas the latter is not. Our proposed methodology for BCI is based on Motor Imagery Signals.

1.3.1 Motor Imagery Signals

Motor imagery is defined as the imagination of a motor action without any efferent information to neuromuscular system. In other words, "imagining a motor movement without actually moving it".

The motor imagery EEG signal is predominant in sensorimotor cortex, corresponding to electrode positions C3 and C4 (according to the international 10-20 system). Oscillations recorded on brain activity in somatosensory and motor areas are referred to as sensorimotor rhythms (SMR). Imagining left hand movement produces a desynchronization on C4 electrode in the right side of the scalp and the imagining right hand movement produces a desynchronization on electrode C3 on the left side of the brain.

Figure 1.1: EEG mean alpha power spatial distribution

The decrease in oscillatory activity in a specific frequency band is referred to as event related desynchronization (ERD) and the increase of oscillatory activity in a specific frequency band is called event related synchronization (ERS). For Motor Imagery, this specific frequency band is between 8-12 Hz. This frequency band is also known as the “mu band”.

In our proposed BCI, the brain signals are acquired through EEG. There are many other alternatives for brain activity monitoring such as functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and Single Photon Emission Computer Tomography (SPECT) which provides better spatial resolution and accuracy. However, the downside is that they are large in size and access to such a device is limited. Whereas EEG is much more portable and provides a better temporal resolution than other modalities.

1.4 Computer to Brain Interface (CBI)

Computer to brain interface is a system that generates and stimulates different brain patterns using a computer. The brain can be stimulated invasively by using a surgically implanted stimulation device and it is known as Deep brain stimulation

(DBS). However, due to immense risks and the invasive nature of DBS many researchers are interested in Non-invasive techniques such as Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) and transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS). Our Proposed methodology for CBI is TMS, where the brain is stimulated using short magnetic pulses.

1.4.1 Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation

Transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) is a well-recognized method for non-invasive neural stimulation. Electromagnetic induction is the major principle in TMS which was developed by Faraday in 1831. A continuously changing magnetic field will induce an electric field in the cortex of the brain in order to depolarize the neurons and generate action potentials. This technique can modulate cortical excitability (either increase or decrease) by changing the parameters of stimulation [7]. TMS has an immense potential in diagnostic, therapeutic, and research area such that it can be used for clinical neurophysiology, rehabilitation and intraoperative monitoring, treatment of neuropsychiatric diseases, evaluate brain physiology and pathophysiology, corticocortical connectivity and brain reactivity and as a computer brain interface [10].

Figure 1.2: Transcranial magnetic stimulation technique

The electromagnetic coil is placed near the scalp, would temporarily excite or inhibit areas of brain with electric pulses induced using powerful magnetic fields. These pulses can be delivered as one at a time (single pulse TMS), as pairs (paired pulse TMS) or as trains (repetitive TMS / rTMS). Stimulus rates more than 1Hz is known as high frequency rTMS and the less is known as low frequency rTMS. Different physiological effects can be obtained by stimulating different lobes or parts of the brain. Most commonly, either the motor cortex of the brain which will produce a muscle twitch or the occipital cortex of the brain that will produce visual phosphenes is stimulated. Corresponding to the part of the motor cortex targeted, different skeletal muscles of the subject will be twitched [11].

Figure 1.3: Lobes of human brain

1.5 Safety

Since the brain to brain interfacing system is used on humans, the safety concerns of the technologies should be investigated. TMS is considered as the safest method to stimulate the brain because of the minimum risk, side effects and discomfort [8,12]. Most of the TMS subjects have not suffered adverse effects, especially from single pulse TMS. However, safety guidelines for TMS research and experiments are established to avoid any safety concerning effect [8].

Inducing a seizure is a main concern of safety. Although occurrence of seizure is highly rare when low frequency or single pulse TMS is used on subjects who do not suffer from epilepsy, multiple sclerosis or use neuroleptic agents. Loud clicking noise

is another safety concern which can cause hearing problems for subjects. This can be mitigated through ear plugs. Burns, headache and discomfort are common problems encountered. Avoiding stimulation of facial muscles and deep brain areas and not using subjects with implants and skin contacted metal objects can minimize such effects [8].

1.6 End Solution and Its Potential Customers

Brain Computer Interface research is gaining popularity among the research community all around the world. Motor Imagery based BCI in particular is gaining more attention as it does not rely on external stimulations. These kind of motor imagery based BCI are useful for communication and control, assisting people with the impaired motor abilities, rehabilitation, gaming and entertainment.

Transcranial magnetic stimulation is another interesting topic of research. This technology is widely used in therapeutic applications in psychiatry, neurology and rehabilitation. There is a potential to extend the single pulse TMS device to an rTMS device that can be used for clinical and therapeutic applications. Basic Circuitry of a TMS device is quite similar to that of an rTMS device. Therefore in the future, with further modifications to the hardware, we can extend the TMS device to an rTMS device. After clinical testing on patients, this device can subsequently be commercialized.

The end solution suggested by the project intends to facilitate the direct brain to brain communication by catering the limitations mentioned above. Possible applications of our study are enormous. However they cannot be achieved immediately. Follow up research will be required in the coming years to make the best out of this study.

People with devastating neuromuscular disorders such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, or ALS, brainstem stroke, cerebral palsy, and spinal cord injury could benefit immensely from this study. This can be used as a media of communication and control as well as for rehabilitation. Let alone the Motor imagery based BCI could make them more independent and make their lives much easier. This system also can be used in the field of Gaming and Entertainment where existing remote controls, communication techniques could be replaced and decisions could simply be made just by thinking.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter reviews the literature available in the area of brain to brain interfacing. First it discusses studies on motor imagery based brain computer interfaces and then it discusses studies on transcranial magnetic stimulation. Finally it reviews the studies that have used both motor imagery based brain to computer interfaces and transcranial magnetic stimulation to form a brain to brain interface.

2.1 Motor Imagery based brain to computer interface

There are related research studies that have been carried out in order to test the potential of motor imagery signals as a BCI candidate. Athena Akrami et al (2005) extracted quantitative changes in EEG signal when imagining left and right hand movement. Logarithmic power of different frequency bands, obtained from different combinations of channels, have been used as the features. Three different classifiers have been tested in the study. Namely, Cluster-Seeking method based on Mahalanobis Distance, Neural Network Classifier and Hidden-Markov-Model (HMM) classifier. Results suggest that applying the linear classifier for frequency features from channels C3 and C4 provide higher classification accuracy [1].

Pawel Herman et al (2008) analysed spectral approaches for motor imagery classification. Techniques such as atomic decomposition, wavelet packets, discrete wavelet transform and quadratic energy distribution were used for feature extraction. The study concludes that the best spectral approach for motor imagery classification is subject specific [2].

Xinyi Yong et al (2015) conducted a study on classifying the motor imagery of different movements within the same limb. Classification was challenging since these movements have close spatial representations on the motor cortex area. They have used Common Spatial Patterns (CSP), Filter-Bank Common Spatial Patterns (FBCSP) and Logarithmic Band power (BP) techniques for feature extraction. Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Logistic Regression (LR) using a fast Bayesian method and Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel have

been used for classification. Proposed BCI system could classify between three states. Namely, rest, imaginary grasp movements and imaginary elbow movements [3].

Hema C.R. et al (2007) proposed a four state motor imagery based Brain Computer Interface. They acquired the EEG from C3 and C4 electrode positions. Features were extracted using the Principle Component Analysis. Two novel classifiers were tested in the study, Elman recurrent neural network and functional link neural network [4].

Roxana Aldea et al (2014) proposed a Motor imagery task classification method using Linear Discriminant Analysis. Wavelet coefficients were used as the features. The system could classify between rest, left and right hand imagery movement. They achieved a maximum classification accuracy of 91% [5].

A.Sivakami et al (2015) carried out multi dimension feature extraction for classification of imagery hand activities. Features were extracted using Discrete Wavelet Transform, FFT Power Spectrum and Event Related Desynchronization (ERD). Back propagation Neural Network has been used for the classification [6].

2.2 Single pulse Transcranial magnetic stimulation

Transcranial Magnetic stimulation is a non-invasive brain stimulation technique with minimal risks, side effects and discomfort. Due to this reason many researchers have adopted this technique in fields of psychiatry, neurophysiology and cognitive neuroscience (J.C Rothwell, 1997) [13]. First attempts of brain stimulation using magnetic fields were conducted by d'Arsonval in 1896 [17]. The diagnostic, therapeutic, and research potential of Transcranial magnetic stimulation was analysed by Paolo and Simone (2007). TMS can be used for clinical neurophysiology (rehabilitation and intraoperative monitoring), treatment of neuropsychiatric diseases to evaluate brain physiology and pathophysiology, corticocortical connectivity and brain reactivity and as a Computer brain interface [11].

2.2.1 Coil design

TMS coil affects the efficiency of stimulation, in terms maximizing the magnetic force and localizing the stimulation. The shape of the coil, inner and outer diameter of the coil and bending angle of coil affect the efficiency of stimulation [10]. There are several TMS coil designs proposed such as Circular coil (O shaped coil),

butterfly coil (eight figured coil), double cone coil, H coil (Hesed coil) and other complex shapes as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: O shape coil and 8 figured coil

The circular coils with large diameters can achieve deep brain stimulation but they have less focality. The most commonly used shape is the figure 8 coil which consists of two adjoining wings. The magnetic field will be concentrated in the central area of figure 8 coil such that fine localization can be obtained through the coil.

The double-cone coil is a modified version of the figure 8 coil where the angle between the two coils is less than 180° . Since the efficiency is reduced when coil elements are non-tangential to the scalp, the angle between the adjoining elements of butterfly coil should be less than 180° . This modification allows the coil to create higher intensities of electric field at deeper areas than the figure 8 coil [18].

Abraham Zangen et al (2004) compared the H coil with the regular 8 figured coil by measuring thresholds for activation. They found out that the H-coil has the ability of deep brain stimulation with low rate of decrease of intensity as it goes deep. The H-coil can stimulate 5.5 cm compared to 2 cm with the figure-8 coil [14].

Leonardo G. Cohen (2003) studied the Effects of coil design on delivery of focal magnetic stimulation and Technical considerations by using several different coils. He found out that out of all the coils, the butterfly shaped coil has induced the largest and most localized magnetic field such that the brain regions can be targeted selectively. However, it is unable to stimulate deep brain areas [15].

Figure 2.2: Magnetic field for (a) circular coil (b) figure 8 coil, Induced electric field for (c) circular coil (d) figure 8 coil

2.2.2 High current pulse generator

The pulse generator is also an important module in TMS device. It is used to supply pulsed electric current to the coil in order to produce the time varying magnetic field near the scalp. A pulse generator consists of a power supply unit, an energy storage unit, a gate driver control circuitry and the load or coil. In designing a pulse generator system parameters such as current requirement, frequency, phase and shape of the pulse needed to be considered.

N. R. Bouda et al (2015) has proposed a method which provides reliable and tuneable pulse shapes. High power MOSFETs or Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) are the proposed topologies. IGBTs are used in applications of low duty cycle, low frequency, and higher voltages while MOSFETs are used in high frequency, high duty cycles and low-voltage applications. Since IGBTs do not need two separate gate drivers as MOSFETs, they are considered to be cost effective [15]

2.3 Brain to Brain Interface

Rajesh P. N. Rao et al (2014) demonstrated how the Brain Computer Interfaces and the Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation can be used to form a direct Brain to Brain interface. The Motor Imagery signals detected from one subject was translated to a command signal and transmitted over the internet to stimulate the brain of a second subject, using Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation [7].

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

The third chapter provides the information about the research methodology. First, it discusses about the EEG signal acquisition strategies, EEG data processing and analysing procedures, Feature extraction methods and classification techniques related to Brain to Computer Interface. Later, it discusses about designing and implementation of TMS coil and pulse generator circuit. Finally, it provides the specifications of the demonstration setup.

3.1 Brain to Computer Interface

The proposed Brain to Computer Interface should have the ability to classify between the subject's left and right upper limb motor intentions, specifically fist closing. Signal Pre-processing and Classification algorithms are developed in order to cater this task.

However, both Motor Imagery and Actual Motor Movement related EEG signals share the same signal characteristics in terms of Event Related Synchronization and Event Related Desynchronization. Therefore, it is a good practice to first develop the classification algorithms for the actual movement signal and then to refine for the Motor Imagery signal. For this reason, initially we have acquired data whilst the subject is performing the actual motor movement. Then the classification algorithms were developed accordingly. As the next step, motor imagery signals were used instead. Additionally, an online dataset which contains both motor movement and imagery EEG signals was also used for the development of classification algorithms.

3.1.1 Graphical User Interface

We have developed a Graphical User Interface that facilitates the process of conducting trials. Signal processing and classification functions were also incorporated to this software. It interacts with the LabChart software to control the functions of the AdInstruments Power Lad amplifier. The software was developed

using Matlab. When the operator clicks on start button, a trial begins and automatically starts the signal recording. Then the system waits for 5 seconds. The recorded EEG corresponding to this period is considered as the reference signal. Then the GUI instructs whether to imagine moving left or right hand (Or perform actual movement). In the next three second period is the time where the subject performs the task. Instruction to move left or right is generated randomly. A random number is generated in the algorithm and if it is odd, the system displays left and if it is even, the system displays right.

Once the trial finishes, the software automatically saves the signals recorded during the 8 seconds period. It also saves the ‘instruction’ (left or right) to the same file. So the output of each trial is a Matlab data file that contains an array of 3 channel EEG record and a string of the instruction. This data are then used as the training data for the classifiers.

GUI also incorporates a function to classify the most recent trial. This classifier is developed using the data gathered over time. It tries to predict the initial instruction and if the prediction is correct it is displayed in green, if not in red.

If the classification (prediction) is correct, it sends the command to the triggering circuit of the TMS device to discharge. This is achieved via an arduino board connected through the USB port.

Figure 3.5: Initial

Figure 3.6: Instruction

Figure 3.7: Classify – correct

Figure 3.8 Classify – wrong

3.1.2 Signal Acquisition

AD Instruments Power Lab is used for the signal acquisition. It supports up to 8 channels, therefore we have the ability to use up to eight electrode positions.

Figure 3.5: EEG Acquisition device

We have used only four electrodes (including ground and reference) in our initial testing. Unipolar signals were obtained from the electrodes corresponding to the C3 and C4 positions in the international 10-20 montage. C3 and C4 are the electrodes in which the motor related EEG activity is most predominant. In the latter stages of the testing, we have also incorporated Cz electrode as well.

Figure 3.6: Electrode Positions

Next we switched from gold-cup electrodes to the ECI cap. Still we stuck to the same electrode positions C3, C4 and Cz. With the ECI cap, the task of subject preparation was much easier. It resulted in better impedance values, usually below 1000 Ohms.

Obtaining a signal which contains event related signal characteristics was a difficult task at first. It took a large number of trials before we could obtain the desired signal. In order to compensate for this delay, we have used another source of data in parallel, for the development of the classification algorithms. That is an online dataset available at Physionet. It contains over 1500 records of both motor imagery and motor movement related EEG. Signals have been acquired using 64 channels. This dataset was used to develop the classification algorithms at the early stage of the project.

3.1.3 Signal Pre-processing

Data pre-processing is an essential stage in the system. Data processing was primarily carried out using Matlab. We have used different techniques in different scenarios. At the signal acquisition level, the software interface (LabChart software) allows us to basic processing. There we carried out band pass filtering to isolate the ‘mu band’. Also we notch filtered the power line noise at 50 Hz.

EEG contains both ocular and EMG artifacts. To get the desired signal, these artifacts should also be removed. Ocular artifact removal follows a spatial filtering method as described below.

- Decompose the signal using ICA

- Dimensions that are composed of a few low frequency components are removed. Ocular artifacts are associated with lower frequencies.
- Reconstruction- Project back to the electrodes.

EMG artifact removal follows a similar procedure except for the fact that the components whose ratio of average power in the typical EEG and EMG bands is below certain threshold are removed. It should be noted that both procedures require a decent electrode density. Therefore this was used only for the online dataset which contained 64 channel EEG data. Matlab EEG lab extension contains tools that facilitate this pre-processing.

3.1.4 Feature Extraction

Different types of features were extracted for the different classifiers tested. All of these features are linked to ‘mu band’ power in some way.

The main feature of interest is the ‘mu band’ power during Event Related Synchronization/Event Related Desynchronization (ERD/ERS). This is quantified with respect to the power during the reference period. Power can be obtained by squaring the amplitude samples.

Another method of classification was tested using features extracted through wavelet transform. This too was tested using both the Physionet data set and data acquired by us. A set of 450 trials (250 for acquired data) was taken and only the C3, C4 and Cz channels were selected. Each EEG record was decomposed into 4 levels using wavelet transform. Different parameters were calculated from the detailed coefficients at levels 2,3 and 4 and tested their performance as features.

For an example, Mean Absolute Value (MAV) of the detailed coefficients at the three levels was one set of testes features. Other parameters that were tested include,

- Root mean square
- Variance of coefficients
- Simple Square Integral
- Positive sum of integrals

Also, different wavelets were tested for decomposition. They were,

- Daubechies
 - Db2, Db4, Db6
- Coiflets
 - Coif2, Coif3, Coif4
- Symlets
 - Sym3, Sym6, Sym10, Sym12

In all of these cases, the feature vector contained 9 elements for each trial.

3.1.5 Classification

Different classifiers were tested for both acquired data and online dataset. Quantified ERD and ERS are classified using a threshold method and other methods incorporated neural networks.

For the wavelet feature based method, a Feed forward Neural Network with one hidden layer and sigmoid activation functions was used for the classifications. Input to the network was the 9 element feature vector. Therefore the input layer contains 9 neurons. Output layer is consisted of 2 neurons. The number of neurons in the hidden layer is changed and tested for the best network which gives the highest classification accuracy. The network was trained using the back propagation algorithm.

3.2 Computer to brain interface

Since the required rate of stimulations for the interactive game is lower than 1Hz, the single pulse TMS device is suitable. A pulse generating device to create such current pulses are implemented. The motor cortex will be stimulated in order to produce a muscle twitch according to the BCI response. Therefore the most suitable coil that will induce a field with maximum focality and intensity is implemented such that different brain regions can be targeted selectively.

3.2.1 Coil design

The most suitable coil design was selected according to the calculations and results obtained by Ansys simulation software. This software uses finite element

analysis to solve three-dimension magnetic fields. By referencing related research papers, existing O shaped coil and figure 8 coil were selected for simulations. According to literature, complex designs such as double cone coil and H- coil are most suitable for deep brain stimulation. According to our requirements, stimulation of deep regions is not that necessary and attempting to stimulate deep regions may cause pain and discomfort to the subject due to high induced fields in cortical areas and facial nerves. Coil designs with iron cores are not selected as they are expensive complex and more suitable for deep brain stimulation.

First the simulations were carried out for flat O shaped and figure 8 shaped coils. Each coil was made up of round shaped wire with 1mm radius. The 3D models of the selected coils with different parameters (dimensions and current ratings) were modelled and electromagnetic field for each were calculated as shown in figure 3.7 (a), (b). Figure 8 coil was used for more advance simulations as it demonstrated highly focused magnetic field compared to O shaped coil. As the current requirement to produce needed magnetic field intensity is very high (4-5 kA) a multi-layer coil design was used. 3D models of figure 8 coils with different no of layers were modelled and the 3D magnetic field simulation plots were obtained as shown in figure 3.7 (c).

Figure 3.7: Ansys 3D model of (a) Flat O shaped coil (b) Flat figure 8 coil (c) multi-layer figure 8 coil (d) figure 8 coil made with rectangle wire

Since the size of the coil is critical, the diameters of the wire needed to be small as possible. However, round or square shaped copper wires with small diameters are unable to withstand large currents (in kA range). Hence rectangular wires with small thickness (< 3 mm) could be used, as they allow more turns while capturing a small space. The braided Litz wire shown in figure 3.8 is more suitable as it has very

low resistance, allows more flexibility and reduces the undesirable effects of induced eddy currents. 3D model for rectangular wire was modelled as shown in figure 3.7 (d) and through the simulation results, optimal design was selected.

Figure 3.8: Braided Litz Copper wire

Cross-sectional information of the circular wire is given by its radius and information of rectangular wire given by height and width as shown in figure 3.9

Figure 3.9: Cross-sectional detail of rectangular wire

The Figure 3.10 shows the magnetic field plots obtained from Ansys simulation software for each 3D models mentioned above. And the following tables show the summarized results obtained from the different simulations.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3.10: Magnitude of the magnetic field obtained for (a) Flat O shaped coil (b) Flat figure 8 coil (c) multi-layer figure 8 coil (d) figure 8 coil made with rectangle wire

Similarly, Ansys simulations were done for figure 8 coil with multiple layers made up with rectangular wire and same coil with a ferrite core. Figure 3.11 shows the Ansys model and simulation results obtained for each coil.

Figure 3.11: Ansys model and magnetic field simulation obtained for Flat figure 8 coil (a) multi-layered (b) single layer with a core

According to above Ansys simulation results, most suitable coil design that can be used to obtain desirable magnetic field intensities and focality was selected. A figure 8 coil with inner diameter of 40mm and outer diameter of 80mm (for single coil) was made using the rectangular Litz wire with 18mm width, 1.5mm thickness and comprised of around 2500 small wires. Individually each wire is insulated with film (tinned) and the whole braided tape is insulated again with PVC insulation tape. After insulation, the coil is wound as a horizontal spiral according to the required dimensions as shown in figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Implemented figure 8 coil

We also constructed both figure 8 coil and O shaped coil to test and verify the results obtained from Ansys simulations. The figure 3.13 shows the magnetic field in vector form that can be obtained from the selected coil design for the 3000A current rating. The implemented coil has a resistance of $100\text{m}\Omega$ and inductance of $8.3\mu\text{H}$

Figure 3.13: Magnetic field in vector form for selected figure 8 coil

3.2.2 Pulse generator circuit

A Pulse generator circuit is designed to create single, monophasic current pulses. The circuit should be able to create kA range current pulse. This is achieved by

simply discharging a large capacitor bank through the coil. The Silicon Controlled Rectifier (SCR) is used as the switching device, as given by figure 3.14. As we need to create 3-4 kA current pulse, an SCR that can handle intermittent current of 9.4kA was selected. The triggering circuit for the SCR was implemented separately.

Resistor R1 is used to act as current limiting resistor in charging circuit and it is also used to discharge when pulse generator is turned off. Resistor R2 act as the current sensing resistor. The R1 resistor is implemented using four 12 Ω (10W) resistors connected in parallel. A wire segment with low resistance is used as R2 resistor and the voltage across that wire segment is captured and measured while discharging the capacitor bank, to calculate the current. External power supply unit to obtain 600-800 VDC from 230V AC was designed as well.

Figure 3.14: Pulse generator circuit

3.2.3 Power Supply

The capacitor Bank in the pulse generator circuit needs to be charged to a very high voltage value (roughly around 800V). The direct power line (230V) is not sufficient for this purpose. Therefore there needs to be a mechanism to step up and convert the 230V AC voltage supply to a high DC output voltage.

The high voltage source is obtained using a voltage multiplier circuit that provides a rectified (DC) output voltage that is a multiple of input peak voltage. This diode capacitor rectifying circuit converts AC to DC and from one stage a 650 VDC supply can be obtained as shown the figure 3.15 below.

Figure 3.15: First stage of voltage multiplier circuit

Matlab Simulink simulations were done for charging and discharging circuits of the capacitor bank to obtain suitable ratings of the capacitor bank including the capacitance and the voltage to which it should be charged and to find rating of the diodes and capacitors of the voltage multiplier circuit. The figure 3.16 and 3.17 shows the Simulink models for charging and discharging circuits of the capacitor bank. According to simulations, capacitor bank should be charged to more than 600V to obtain current pulse of 3kA. The capacitance of the capacitor bank should be around 1800uF.

Figure 3.16: Simulink model for discharging circuit

Figure 3.17: Simulink model for charging circuit

Ceramic capacitors with voltage rating of more than 650V should be used for the voltage multiplier. The capacitance of the capacitors are $1\mu\text{F}$ such that the capacitor bank will be charged quickly. According to simulation results, Diodes that can withstand 1kV and 1A are chosen. And the capacitor bank can be charged up to 650V within less than 2 minutes.

The following figure 3.18 shows the power supply unit which was implemented to obtain 650VDC to charge the capacitor bank.

Figure 3.18: Power supply unit

3.2.4 Capacitor bank

The capacitor bank consists of 6 Aluminium Electrolytic capacitors, each with 1200 μF capacitance and 400VDC rating. Three strings of capacitors, where each string consist of two capacitors connected in series, are connected in parallel such that the resultant capacitance of the bank is 1800 μF and has voltage rating of 800VDC.

Figure 3.19: The capacitor bank

3.2.5 SCR and triggering circuit

Since we used a hockey puck SCR as shown in figure 3.20, a separate connection piece was constructed to connect anode and cathode of SCR to the pulse generator circuitry. The gate of the SCR and auxiliary cathode are connected to the triggering circuit.

Figure 3.20: Hockey puck SCR

The figure 3.21 shows the SCR with its connection terminals. The purpose of the triggering circuit is to produce a positive pulse at the gate in order to trigger the SCR. The triggering pulse of 150mA with pulse width of 20 μ s is obtained using a TIP31A NPN silicon transistor, Arduino board and biasing resistors. The figure 3.22 illustrates the triggering circuit of the SCR. The resistance of R1 R2 R3 resistors are 27 Ω (1W), 220 Ω (0.25W) and 1k Ω (0.25W) respectively. By applying a 5V for 20 μ s using the microcontroller, the required triggering pulse is obtained.

Figure 3.21: The silicon controlled rectifier

Figure 3.22: The triggering circuit

Implemented SCR with the triggering circuit is given by the figure 3.23 given below.

Figure 3.23: SCR with triggering circuit

3.3 Demonstration Setup

The control of one subject's motor movement(s) by another subject's Motor Imagery (MI) signals. Example: real time control over a game using another person's command. The player who observes the game (sender) is coupled with a BCI and motor Imagery signal is used to send the command. The player who has access to the game controls (receiver) is coupled with a Computer Brain Interface which stimulates the brain according to the received signal which ultimately results in a muscle twitch.

Real time EEG is recorded from the sender and Motor Imagery (MI) signal is identified from the subject (sender). Our Algorithm classifies the motor imagery and the identified state is converted into a control signal. Next the command is transferred to the microcontroller (Arduino) using USB. This will trigger the SCR device. Then the Receiver's motor cortex is stimulated via TMS (Transcranial magnetic stimulation) which results in a muscle twitch.

Chapter 4

RESULTS

This chapter presents the Experimental results that were obtained on Brain to Brain Interface and Computer to brain interface.

4.1 Brain to Computer Interface

The Figure 4.1 and 4.2 depict a two scalp power distribution map generated at 10 Hz. It is clearly evident that during the motor movement period, contra lateral side of the motor cortex is desynchronized. That means when we move our right hand, EEG activity on our left side of the brain is desynchronized and vice versa. This conforms to what we learnt during our literature review. Blue represents low power and red represents high power.

Figure 4.1: Scalp power distribution during Right Fist close

Wavelet based Neural Network classifier was tested using both the Physionet online dataset and acquired data. A set of 450 trials (250 for acquired data) was taken. For each trial, a feature vector was constructed as explained in the previous chapter. Neural Network was trained to classify this feature vectors into two classes. 70% of

the sample data was used to train the network and another 15% for validation and the last 15% for testing.

Figure 4.2: Scalp power distribution during Left Fist close

This training and testing procedure was repeated again and again for different networks with different numbers of hidden neurons. Each time the classification accuracy for the testing process is recorded.

This Entire procedure was repeated for different wavelets in the initial stage. Daubechies, Coiflets and Symlets families of wavelets were tested. The results obtained from the above analysis for the dataset acquired, are summarized below. Each graph represents classification accuracies against a number of neurons in the hidden layer. Classification accuracy is computed by taking the ratio of number of correct classifications to the total number of trials in the testing stage. And the feature vector is a 9 element vector composed of Mean Absolute Values of detailed coefficients of wavelet decomposition at levels 2, 3 and 4 (for each of the three channels c3, c4 and cz).

Figure 4.3: Classification accuracies for Daubechies wavelet

A maximum classification accuracy of 65% was recorded for the network with 13 neurons. The signal was decomposed using Db2 wavelet.

Figure 4.4: Classification accuracies for Coiflets wavelet

A maximum classification accuracy of 69% was recorded for the network with 10 neurons. The signal was decomposed using Coif2 wavelets.

Figure 4.5: Classification accuracies for Symlets wavelet

A maximum classification accuracy of 65% was recorded for the network with 11 neurons. The signal was decomposed using Sym12 wavelets. Below table summarizes the maximum average classification accuracies obtained for different parameters other than Mean Absolute Value.

Table 4.1: Classification accuracies for different parameters

Parameter	Accuracy
Root mean square	Less than 55%
Variance of coefficients	Around 65%
Simple Square Integral	Less than 55%
Positive sum of integrals	Less than 55%

4.2 Computer to Brain Interface

The following tables 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 illustrates the Ansys simulation results obtained for different coil models. According to the simulation results, the figure 8 coil showed maximum focality. Using a current pulse of 3kA a magnetic field around 1 tesla can be obtained.

Table 4.2: Ansys simulation results for circular wires

Shape	Current rating (A)	Cross-section radius(mm)	Inner radius (mm)	Number of layers	Turns	Tesla (T)
O	300	1	26.25	1	10	0.114
O	300	1	27.25	1	6	0.106
O	300	1	35	1	6	0.105
O	500	1.75	27.25	1	6	0.115
O	500	1.75	20	1	9	0.221
O	2000	1.75	20	1	9	0.526
O	3000	1.75	20	1	9	0.738
O	5000	1.75	20	1	9	1.22
Butterfly	300	1	25	1	6	0.107
Butterfly	300	1	27.25	1	6	0.108
Butterfly	300	1	30	1	6	0.118
Butterfly	300	1	36	1	6	0.108
Butterfly	400	1	27.25	1	6	0.168
Butterfly	1500	1	27.25	1	6	0.540
Butterfly	500	1.75	20	1	9	0.127
Butterfly	1500	1.75	20	1	9	0.382
Butterfly	2000	1.75	20	1	9	0.510
Butterfly	2000	1.75	27.25	1	6	0.490
Butterfly	4000	1.75	27.25	1	6	0.978
Butterfly	3000	1.75	20	1	9	0.765
Butterfly	3500	1.75	20	1	9	0.89
Butterfly	4000	1.75	20	1	9	1.01
Butterfly	5000	1.75	20	1	9	1.27
Butterfly	2500	1.75	20	2	9	1.18
Butterfly	1250	1.75	20	4	9	0.94
Butterfly	1500	1.75	20	4	9	1.129

Table 4.3: Ansys simulation results for rectangular wires

Shape	Current (A)	Height (mm)	Width (mm)	Inner radius (mm)	Number of layers	Turns	Tesla (T)
Butterfly	4000	1	10	27.25	1	6	1.446
Butterfly	4000	1.5	12.5	20	1	9	1.534
Butterfly	3000	1.5	12.5	20	1	9	1.069
Butterfly	4000	3	25	20	1	8	0.766
Butterfly	3000	1.5	18	25	1	8	1.047
Butterfly	1000	1.5	18	25	3	8	0.527

Table 4.4: Ansys simulation results for coil with a ferrite core

Shape	Current (A)	Height (mm)	Width (mm)	Innerradius (mm)	Turns	Tesla (T)
Butterfly	3000	1	10	27.25	6	1.541

Simulations of the power supply circuit with the capacitor bank shows promising results. According to Simulink simulations, the Capacitor bank was charged to the desired voltage in less than 2 minutes. According to simulations done for discharging circuit, a current pulse as shown in the figure 4.6 can be obtained.

Figure 4.6: Discharging current pulse

The figure 4. 7 illustrates the complete pulse generator circuitry of the TMS device.

Figure 4.7: Pulse generator circuit

Using a small wire with $1.85\text{m}\Omega$ resistance (R1) the current through the coil was calculated. Voltage across that wire when the current pulse is passed through the coil was measured using a digital oscilloscope (using triggering mode). The pulse captured by the oscilloscope is given by the figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Captured pulse using Oscilloscope

The table 4.5 shows the estimated (using matlab simulations) and measured (using R1 resistor) peak current in the TMS device for different supply voltages.

Table 4.5: Current through the coil

Supply voltage (DC)	Voltage across wire	Calculated current	Estimated current (matlab)
20V	212mV	114.6A	130A
40V	432 mV	233.5 A	260A
80V	890 mV	481.1 A	520A
100V	1120 mV	605.4 A	650A
110V	1300 mV	702.7 A	710A
150V	1740 mV	940.5 A	980A
200V	2140 mV	1156.8 A	1300A
215V	2200 mV	1189.2 A	1450A
390V	3800mV	2054.1A	2550A
500V	7600mV	4108.1A	3300A
610V	13000mV	7027.0A	4250A

Chapter 5

DISCUSSION

This chapter illustrates the encountered challenges during the execution of the project. It also briefs the next steps and related future work.

5.1 Challenges Faced

5.1.1 *Brain to Computer Interface*

Motor Imagery based Brain to Computer Interfaces is a hot topic of research. Therefore there are numerous publications available online which have utilized different methods for signal processing. The information content was so overwhelming that initially it was difficult to select the best methods. Therefore it required a considerable amount of time to go through the literature.

The next challenge arose when we started acquiring EEG from the subjects. Getting the impedance below 5000 Ohms was a difficult task at first. Therefore a considerable amount of time was spent on subject preparation. Once the impedance issue was resolved, the next challenge was to obtain a signal that represents event related signal characteristics. EEG is distorted from external noise sources and other artifacts. At times in some subjects Motor Imagery/Movement related ERDs are not observable. Therefore the system needed a lot of calibrations before we could obtain the desired signal.

These delays in signal acquisition posed a barrier for the development of algorithms, because it needed data to train the classifiers. To overcome this issue, at the early stages, we have used an online data set available at Physionet, for the development of classifiers. These tested classifiers were then refined using the data acquired by us.

Another challenge was the ambiguity in imagination. As opposed to motor movement, there was no proper way to guarantee that the subject carries out the motor imagery successfully. There is no visual cue to confirm whether the motor imagery is carried out successfully.

Subject specificity of the Motor Imagery signals posed us another challenge. Classifier needed to be trained specifically to one particular subject.

5.1.2 *Computer to Brain Interface*

Since the human brain is simulated using large magnetic fields, safety is a major concern when using transcranial magnetic stimulation as the computer interface. Therefore it required a considerable amount of effort to go through safety guidelines and literature in order to clarify and resolve the safety issues of TMS.

Designing the current pulse generator was another challenge due to its high current requirement. The components of the circuit such as SCR, capacitor bank and power supply unit have high component ratings and voltage requirement. Hence they made the problem more complex and challenging.

Time taken to charge the capacitor bank was another obstacle and the time depends on the capacitance ratio between the capacitor bank and the capacitors in the voltage multiplier circuit. Since the ceramic capacitors with high capacitance and voltage rating are limited reducing the time taken to charge was challenging.

Validation of the intensity and the focality of magnetic field generated in the coil was another challenging situation that was faced. There was no proper device (gauss meter or flux meter) to measure and quantify the transient magnetic field. Iron oxide powder was used to confirm whether a magnetic field is generated.

5.2 **Future Work**

5.2.1 *Brain to Computer Interface*

- Classifiers could potentially be improved with increased number of training data. Currently it has been trained using only 250 trials.
- In this study, we have only explored the possibility of classify between two classes of motor imagery. This work can be extended to multi-class classifications in the same limb. For an example, to classify between elbow flexion/extension, wrist movement in the upper limb.

5.2.2 *Computer to brain Interface*

- Design advanced TMS coil with a ferrite core to obtain stronger localized magnetic field with low current ratings.

- Improve the existing device for a repetitive TMS (rTMS) device which can be used for therapeutic purposes.

5.3 Conclusion

5.3.1 Brain to Computer Interface

It is evident from the results that the neural network with 10 neurons in the hidden layer performs the best among all the classifiers tested. Input to this classifier is a feature vector of nine elements composed of Mean Absolute Values of detailed coefficients of coiflet wavelet decomposed signals at levels 2,3 and 4. (for each electrode c3,c4 and cz).

Figure 5.1: Neural Network classifier

5.3.2 Computer to brain Interface

It is evident from the results that obtain magnetic fields of 1 to 3 Tesla, currents in kilo Ampere ranges are needed. And using such strong magnetic field the neural system can be stimulated in order to control the motor movement of the subjects.

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